

Benthic Molluscan Diversity and Environmental Indicators : A Review from Freshwater Reservoirs

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ABSTRACT

An important group of freshwater invertebrates, benthic molluscs are essential for maintaining the biological equilibrium of aquatic environments. Freshwater reservoirs in India are location to a wide variety of molluscan species that are useful environmental indicators. The research on benthic molluscan diversity from several Indian reservoirs is collected in this review, which further focuses on the ecological significance of this information. In benthic ecosystems, the main groups—including gastropods and bivalves—contribute to energy transfer, sediment stability, and nutrient cycling. These species are useful to assess water quality and ecosystem changes because their abundance and presence often indicate the general health of aquatic ecosystems. The study highlights the importance of conducting detailed studies on benthic molluscs in India's various freshwater bodies in order to ensure the preservation of biodiversity and the sustainable management of reservoir ecosystems.

Keywords: Molluscan Diversity, Freshwater reservoirs, Environmental indicators, Ecosystem Health, India.

INTRODUCTION

India's freshwater habitats support an extremely high diversity of molluscan fauna, with around 212 species belonging to 21 families, 164 of which have been reported in rivers and streams (Subba Rao, 1993). Molluscan population abundance and distribution are useful ecological indicators because their presence often indicates favorable environmental conditions. Most molluscs are unable to survive in acidic environments below pH 5 (Boycott, 1934), hence their presence is closely associated to the chemical quality and stability of aquatic habitats. It is well known that biological monitoring of freshwater systems with macroinvertebrates is a useful method for evaluating ecosystem health and water quality (Hellowell, 1986). Molluscs hold an important place significant such organisms because of their ecological importance, wide range, and sensitivity to environmental changes (Ruppert et al., 2004; Brusca et al., 2016). The group of the second-largest phylum in the animal kingdom is called Mollusca. Its name comes from the Latin word mollus, which means "soft," referring to the soft bodies that are usually protected in hard calcareous shells (Brusca et al.,

2016; Pechenik, 2015). According to Srivastava (1992), there are about 85,000 species of molluscs that have been described worldwide. These species are divided into seven major taxonomic classes: Aplacophora (worm like mollusks without shells), Polyplacophora (chitons with eight shell plates), Monoplacophora (single cap like shell; e.g., *Neopilina*), Gastropoda (snails, slugs), Scaphopoda (tusk shells), Pelecypoda (*Lamellidens marginalis*), Cephalopoda. Molluscs indicate a variety of life-history strategies, complicated ecological interactions, and a wide range of freshwater habitats (Seddon et al., 2010). By controlling water quality, nitrogen dynamics, and algal populations through grazing and filter-feeding, they play a major role in maintaining wetland and reservoir ecosystems (Vaughn 2018). They also link primary producers to predators by acting as a vital food supply for higher trophic levels. According to Sarwade et al. (2015), benthic molluscs are therefore important for biogeochemical cycling and serve as useful environmental markers of the stability and health of freshwater ecosystems.

Diversity

Mollusca is the world's second biggest animal phylum, with an estimated variety of roughly 0.2 million species, of which approximately 85,000 have been described (Rosenberg, 2014). This contains roughly 52,525 marine, 24,000 terrestrial, and 7,000 freshwater species (Chapman, 2009). Around 5,070 Molluscs species have been reported in India, with 3,370 of them living in marine habitats (V.Subba Rao, 1991). India's freshwater molluscan fauna is primarily represented by the classes Gastropoda and Bivalvia, with approximately 217 species—150 gastropods and 67 bivalves—distributed across the mainland and islands (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2017). According to Hogarth (2001), biodiversity includes all of the variation found in all living forms at all organizational levels, from genes to ecosystems. DeLong (1996) continued on to highlight biodiversity as an aspect of a region that represents the diversity of living things, communities, and biotic processes, whether they are natural or affected by human activity. Molluscan diversity, which reflects the biological complexity and environmental stability of freshwater reservoirs in India, is a crucial component of aquatic biodiversity in this context.

Classification and freshwater common species of phylum Mollusca

Common species of freshwater molluscs found in rivers, lakes, and reservoirs include bivalves like *Lamellidens marginalis* and gastropods like *Pila globosa* and *Lymnaea stagnalis* (Subba Rao, 1989; Ramakrishna & Dey, 2007). Cephalopods like *Octopus vulgaris* and *Loligo vulgaris*, as well as bivalves like *Pinctada fucata*, are the most common molluscan species in marine habitats. These species are significant both ecologically and commercially in coastal ecosystems (FAO, 2016; Rosenberg, 2014). Based on morphological, anatomical, and molecular traits, the phylum Mollusca—one of the most varied animal phyla—is commonly separated into a number of major taxonomic divisions (Haszprunar, 2001; Ponder & Lindberg, 2008; Kocot et al., 2011). According to the diversity of species reported, it is regarded as the second-largest animal phylum (Rosenberg, 2014).

Class Bivalvia or Pelecypoda

Examples: Anodonta, Unio, Ostrea, Teredo

One or two pairs of gills are present on bivalves, which have a laterally compressed body enclosed in two hinged valves. Primarily filter feeders, they are ecologically significant in aquatic environments (Ponder & Lindberg, 2008; Rosenberg, 2014).

Class Gastropoda

Examples: Pila, Cypraea, Conus, snails and slugs

The largest and most varied class of molluscs, gastropods, undergo bends as they grow. They live on land, in freshwater, and in the ocean (Bouchet et al., 2017).

Economic Importance of Molluscs

Because of their many functions in the food supply, industry, ecosystem functioning, and biomedical research, molluscs are of great economic, ecological, and social significance. Both freshwater and marine molluscs provide ecosystem services that support aquatic productivity and directly improve human well-being (Gosling, 2003; Barker, 2001).

Food and Fisheries

Several bivalves and gastropod species are rich in nutrients food sources. Freshwater species like *Lamellidens marginalis*, *Parreysia corrugata*, and *Bellamya bengalensis* are consumed locally in India, providing a source of income for rural families

(Ayyakkannu and Mahadevan, 1976). Molluscs such as clams, oysters, and mussels comprise a significant share of the global aquaculture and fisheries business (FAO, 2022).

Pearl and Shell Industry

It is known that some freshwater bivalves, such as *Lamellidens corrianus* and *Parreysia favidens*, can provide naturally occurring pearls of both decorative and commercial value. Their shells are utilized in the production of jewelry and ornamental products, as well as in the button, lime, cement, and handicraft industries (Goswami, 2015). Additionally, crushed shells are used as a calcium supplement in medications and poultry feed.

Environmental Indicators

Because of their susceptibility to pollutants and ability to bioaccumulate heavy metals, molluscs serve as bioindicators of environmental health. Molluscan community monitoring helps in identifying changes in water quality and evaluating the ecological condition of freshwater reservoirs (Tripathi et al., 2020; Pandit & Kumar, 2019).

Threat to Molluscs

In freshwater systems, particularly in the Western Ghats, illegal and uncontrolled sand mining rapidly degrades ecosystems and reduces benthic biodiversity. Sensitive molluscan species may decline or become extinct immediately as a result of sand extraction and the process of which also change the structure of rivers, increase turbidity, and decrease diversity in habitats (Dudgeon et al., 2006). Bivalves are particularly susceptible to changes in soil porosity and water quality put on by sediment disturbance because they are predators and filter feeders. Mining and the disposal of organic garbage close to the Thaneermukham Barrage have significantly impacted freshwater mollusk species, according to studies from Vembanad Lake (Laxmilatha & Appukuttan, 2002).

The endangered bivalve *Pseudomulleria dalyi* is only found in a few areas in the Western Ghats and is threatened by dam construction, pollution, and habitat disturbance in rivers such as Tunga and Bhadra (Aravind et al., 2011).

Pollution

Pollution of freshwater ecosystems from agricultural runoff, sewage discharge, industrial effluents, and

excessive harvesting pose a major threat to molluscan diversity, particularly in the Western Ghats. Effluents from shrimp and fish processing businesses, mining, and paper and textile mills significantly decrease water quality and sediment conditions (Jayachandran et al., 2019).

Monsoon-related excessive erosion, sedimentation, and deforestation further decrease the habitat variability necessary for bivalve survival. As filter feeders, bivalves are highly sensitive to pollution and easily collect toxins, making them useful markers of water quality (Salánki et al., 2003). On the other hand, tolerant gastropod species including *Gyraulus convexiusculus*, *Lymnaea luteola*, *L. acuminata*, and *Indoplanorbis exustus* frequently survive in contaminated environments. The Tunga River's limited distribution of the endangered bivalve *Pseudomulleria dalyi* emphasizes the critical need for conservation efforts and research to deal with rising pollution (Madhyastha, 2001).

Overharvesting

Many freshwater bivalves, including *Lamellidens*, *Corbicula*, and *Parreysia*, are collected for human consumption, especially in the coastal areas of Kerala and Karnataka. Inappropriate harvesting can cause habitat disturbance and population decrease, but moderate harvesting might not be immediately dangerous. In Kerala, commercially desirable species including *Villorita cyprinoides* & *V. cornucopia* are at risk of over endangering their natural populations (Nandan et al., 2012; Jayachandran et al., 2019). Because over fishing of its host fish species in the Tunga River has significantly reduced its population, the endangered bivalve *Pseudomulleria dalyi* is particularly susceptible. To ensure these species' long-term survival, sustainable harvesting methods and population tracking are essential (Rajesh et al., 2020).

Conservation recommendations

Research Actions

The Western Ghats and the Northeastern Himalayas provide the majority of India's freshwater molluscan diversity data, with little research done in other areas (Aravind & Jadhav, 2023; Budha et al., 2011). Understanding freshwater molluscs' ecosystem functions, distribution patterns, population dynamics, and the effects of aquatic invasive species should be the main goals of future research. Changing the taxonomy and conservation status of species with

little data, including ecological and life-history research, requires extra care. Biodiversity databases can be improved and species identification made easier by revisiting type sites and specimens (Dayrat, 2005; Bickford et al., 2007).

Conservation for Livelihood of People

Freshwater molluscs are essential to maintaining local practices and ways of life. In several parts of India, species including *Parreysia sp.*, *Lamellidens sp.*, *Corbicula sp.*, and *Villorita spp.* are eaten. In Kerala and the Aghanashini estuary on India's west coast, the black clam fishery, which depends on *Villorita cornucopia* and *V. cyprinoides*, has significant economic value (Remani et al., 2010; Bijkumar et al., 2013). Furthermore, *Pila globosa* is widely utilized in traditional medical practices; in southern India, its flesh is used to cure poultry wounds and sore eyes (Boominathan et al., 2008). Instead of depending only on wild gathering, encouraging sustainable breeding and aquaculture of such species will guarantee the preservation of natural populations while maintaining rural livelihoods.

CONCLUSION

Benthic molluscs are essential parts components freshwater reservoirs, providing significantly to ecosystem balance, sediment stability, and nutrient cycling. Because they reflect changes in habitat conditions and water quality, their variety and abundance are useful indicators of environmental health. However, their numbers are declining as a result of problems like pollution, sand mining, and overharvesting. To save these economically and ecologically significant species, conservation efforts, regular monitoring, and sustainable management techniques are essential. Maintaining the ecological integrity of freshwater ecosystems will benefit from increased research on their diversity, ecology, and potential as bioindicators.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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